

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

RATIONAL APPROACH TOWARDS THE ROLE OF *KALAWNJI* (*NIGELLA SATIVA* LINN) IN *MARZ - E - AKYAS KHUSYATUR REHM* (POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME)-A REVIEW

Md Sheeraz^{1*}, Arsheed Iqbal¹, Naquibul Islam¹, Abdur Rasheed², Haider Ali Quraishi¹, Shameem Rather¹, Ruqaya Qayoom¹, Md Danish¹

¹Department of Moalajat, Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine, Srinagar, J and K.

²Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine, Bhadrak, Orissa.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 11/05/2018

Available online

31/05/2018

Keywords

Kalawnji,
Nigella Sativa linn,
Marz - e - Akyas
Khusyatur Rehm,
Polycystic Ovarian
Syndrome,
Unani medicine.

ABSTRACT

Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) is one of the commonest Endocrine disorders. It usually presents during adolescence with menstrual irregularities and weight gain, and with or without signs of hyperandrogenism such as acne and hirsutism. It often affects several family members and is aggravated by obesity. The incidence varies between 0.5 - 4 %. It is prevalent in young reproductive age group (20 -30%). Polycystic ovary may be seen in about 20% of normal women. In Unani System of Medicine, the disease has not been mentioned under the term of PCOS but the description of the disease has been described vividly by various Unani physicians under the headings of *qillate tams* (Oligomenorrhoea), *ehtebas tams* (amenorrhoea), *uqr* (Infertility). The best known treatment of PCOS at present is by using allopathic medicines such as clomiphene citrate, metformin and tamoxifen. All these have mild to severe side effects including hot flushes, anorexia, nausea, metallic taste, flatulence, abdominal pain, mild diarrhoea, tiredness, vertigo and allergic dermatitis. So there is a need for alternative treatment. In order to provide safe and more effective medicine for PCOS, a meticulous attempt has been made in this review study to explore the utility of this age old drug *Kalawnji* (*Nigella Sativa* linn) in the management of PCOS.

Corresponding author

Dr. Mohammed Sheeraz

Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine,
Kashmir University,
Srinagar, J and K. 190006.
email:sheeraz.rrium@gmail.com
7051727703.

Please cite this article in press as **Dr. Mohammed Sheeraz et al. Rational Approach Towards the Role of *Kalawnji* (*Nigella Sativa* Linn) in *Marz - E - Akyas Khusyatur Rehm* (Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome)-A Review. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018:8(05).**

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Unani system of medicine has grown out of fusion and thoughts of diverse knowledge and experiences. Its origin can be traced back to the fourth and fifth century B.C when it was first propounded by Bukhrat (Hippocrates) in Greece. According to its principles and philosophy, maintenance of health, disease and its manifestations are innate process, hence proper and normal functioning of the bodily process must be ensured to maintain health. Any disturbance in the normal humoral balance whether it is excess, diminution or blockage leads to disease. Unani scholars managed certain ailments since antiquity by regulating the metabolic process through various modes of treatment. According to Unani system of Medicine the principles of treatment are: 1. Ilaj bit tadbeer waTaghzia (Regimenal and Dieto therapy) 2. Ilaj bid dawa (Drug therapy) 3. Ilajbilyad (Surgery).

Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) is one of the commonest Endocrine disorders. It describes a constellation of clinical and biochemical features. It usually presents during adolescence with menstrual irregularities and weight gain, and with or without signs of hyperandrogenism such as acne and hirsutism. It often affects several family members and is aggravated by obesity.[1] It is heterogeneous collection of signs and symptoms that gathered together form a spectrum of disorder with a mild presentation in some, while in others a severe disturbance of reproductive, endocrine and metabolic function.[2] The incidence varies between 0.5 - 4 %. It is prevalent in young reproductive age group (20 -30%). Polycystic ovary may be seen in about 20% of normal Women.[3]

Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) was originally described in 1935 by Stein and Leventhal as a syndrome associated with enlarged polycystic ovaries. PCOS is diagnosed on the basis of a combination of clinical or biochemical evidence of hyperandrogenism, amenorrhea or oligomenorrhoea, and the ultrasound appearance of polycystic ovaries. Approximately half of patients with PCOS are obese, and abnormalities in insulin dynamics are common as in metabolic syndrome. Symptoms generally begin shortly after menarche and are slowly progressive. [4][5][6][7][8] The patient complains of increasing obesity (abdominal – 50%), menstrual abnormalities (70%) in the form of oligomenorrhoea, amenorrhea and infertility. [4-8] Presence of hirsutism and acne are the important features. Hirsutism was later noted in up to 50% of the patients. [1][4][9] Typically, the ovaries are enlarged. Presence of multiple (> 12) follicular cysts measuring about 2- 9 mm in diameter are found crowded around the cortex [3]

In Unani System of Medicine, the disease has not been mentioned under the term of PCOS, but the description of the disease has been described vividly by various Unani physicians under the headings of *qillate tams* (Oligomenorrhoea), *ehtebas tams* (amenorrhea), *uqr* (Infertility). [5]The cause of infertility in females due to obesity and PCOS as described by modern medicine are very much similar to the causes and features of *Uqr* in Unani medicine, but hormonal concept in relation to this disorder is recent. [7] It is described that women with secondary amenorrhea presenting the features of male, like hoarseness of voice, hirsutism.[5][10] Since PCOS is manifested with symptoms of amenorrhea, infertility, obesity and hirsutism, various descriptions related to the above conditions are found in classical Unani literature that women become amenorrhoeic if her *mizaj* transformed towards masculinity and develops the features, like male pattern hair growth, hoarseness of voice.[5][10] Hirsutism is mentioned in classical Unani literature as a complication of prolonged amenorrhea associated with other masculine features like appearance of hair on body.[5] The best known treatment of PCOS at present is by using allopathic medicines such as clomiphene citrate, metformin and tamoxifen. All these have mild to severe side effects including hot flushes, anorexia, nausea, metallic taste, flatulence, abdominal pain, mild diarrhoea, tiredness, vertigo and allergic dermatitis.[6] So there is a need for alternative treatment. The drugs in Unani System of medicine, which correct *ehtebas tams*, *uqr* and *sui mizaj barid* are generally found to be useful in PCOS. *Mudir haiz* drugs have *mudir* (emenagogue) and *mulatiff* properties, so it regulates menstrual cycles. Unani physicians mentioned a number of single and compound drugs that can be used in the management of Signs and Symptoms of PCOS, but these drugs have not been scientifically validated so far, for their described effects. *Kalawnji* (*Nigella Sativa* linn) is one of the drug which are useful in signs and symptoms of PCOS,[11][12][13][14][15] has been selected for the study. *Kalawnji* (*Nigella sativa* linn) 4.5 grams[16] orally will be taken in the form of Safoof is recommended by Ibne huble Bughdadi.

In order to provide safe and more effective medicine for PCOS, the present review study entitled “Rational Approach Towards The Role of *Kalawnji* (*Nigella Sativa* linn) in *Marz - e - Akyas Khusyatur Rehm* (Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome) is attempted, so that clinical trials can be conducted on the basis of review of this literature.

Kalawnji

Introduction:

Kalawnji (*Nigella sativa*) is a herb, its seed is used in treatment of various diseases. Its seed and oil have a long history of folklore usage in Arabian and Indian civilization and are used in food as well as medicine[17] It is used as condiment in carries, also used as spice[18]. According to Tibbe Nabvi Prophet Muhammed (saw) has told that, You, use this *Shoneez* because it has cure for all diseases except death[19].

Botanical name: *Nigella sativa* Linn [17][18][19][20][21][22][23][24][26][27]

Family: Ranunculaceae [17][18][20][21][22][23][24][25][26][27][28]

Vernacular name:

Arabic	: Habbatul Sauda [20] [29] [30] [31] Kabodan [32]. Kamun Aswad, Shoneez [18] [20] Kamoona Hindi [29].
Persian	: Siyah Dana [20] [56] [29] [31]. Shoneez [20] [29] [30] [31] [33].
Urdu	: Kalawnji [20] [21].
Hindi	: Kalawnji, Mangraila [21] Kalajira [17][21][23][27].
English	: Small Funnel, Black Cumin [18] [20] [56] [25] [27] [28].
Bengali	: Mangrela [27], Kala Zeera [18] [20] [23] [27] [28]
Gujrati	: Kalaunji Jirum [23][20][28] Kadujeeroo [18][23]
Kannada	: Karijirige [20][21][23][27][28].
Kashmiri	: Tukhme Gandana [18][20].
Marathi	: Kalaunji-jire, kalerjire [20].
Malyalam	: Karinchirakam [21][27][28]
Panjabi	: Kavanji [20].
Tamil	: Karunjarakam[20], Karunjiragam [20][21][23][27][28].
.Telgu	: Peeajila Kara[20], Nallajilakara [20][23][56][28]
Sanskrit	: Sthula Jiraka, Susavi[20], Krishna jiraka [18][20] Upakuncika, Karvi [56][28]
Sindhi	: Kalodi [34].
Unani	: Kamaazaruus [25], Sino, Sheenon [32].
Turki	: Qarachurak Audi [32].

Description:**Habitat:**

In India it cultivated in Panjab [21][17][26][28], Bihar [17][26][28], Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pardesh, Assam and Bengal[17][26], and also around world i.e. Europe [28][35], North Africa, Egypt, Pakistan, Iran, Iraq and Turkey [35].

Nigella sativa is a pretty herb, 30-60 cm high, leave 2-3 pinnatisect, 2.5-5 cm long, cut into linear lanceolate segments. Flowers pale blue on solitary long peduncles 2-2.5 cm across. Septal ovate, acute, clawed. Nectorial plates 8, geniculate with saccate gland in the knee, one on the face and one on the apex of each lobe. Carpels 67, inflated wart at the side united to top. Beak as long as ovary [21][22][28].

Part used: Seed [21][22][23][26], Fruit [21][23].

Seed morphology:**Macroscopic:**

Triangonus, black, regulose tubercular [17][21][26][28][36]. Test is bitter[28]. Odour slightly aromatic[20]. It is small about 2-3 mm long and 1 mm wide, tapering toward umbilical side. The seed coat is rough papillose, very thin. It encloses a dull white oily kernel. The embryo is small embedded in the oily endosperm toward pointed end of seed [21].

Microscopic:

Transverse section of seed show single layer of epidermis consisting of elliptical, thick walled cells covered externally a papillose cuticle filled with reddish- brown content. Endosperm consist a moderate thick walled rectangular to polygonal cells, a few filled with oil globules [20].

Af'aa (Actions):

Munaffise Balgham (Expectorant)^{[20][30][33][34]}

Muhallile Riyah (Carminative)[19][30][34][37]

Muqawwi Meda(Stomachic)[20][30][34]

Mulayyan(Laxative)[30][34]

Qatile Kirme Shikam (Antihelmenthic)[20][30][34][37][38][39]

Mukhrife Deedan(Vermifuge)[19][29][40]

Mudire Bol(Diuretic)^{[19][29][30][31][33][34][37]}

Mudire Haiz(Emenagogue)[19][29][30][31] [33][34][37][39][40]

Musakkine Alam(Analgesic)[20, 30, 34]

Mufatteh Sudad (Deobstruant)[19]

Mufattite Hisat(Lithortiptic)^{[19][29][33][39][40]}

Mudire Laban(Galactogogue)[19][29]

Mukhrife Janeen(Abortifaciant)[29][31][33]

Dafe Humma(Antipyretic)[61][33][39]

Muhallile Auram(Antinflammatory)[20]

Munzije Mawad (Concoctive)[30][31]**Istemaal (Therapeutic actions):**

Dakhili Istemal (Internal uses):

Zoofe Meda (Weakness of stomach) [20][30][34]
 Nafakhe Shikam (Flatulence) [19][20][30][34]
 Darde Shikam (Gastralgia) [30] [34]
 Qoulanj (Colic) [20][29][30][33][34]
 Istesqa (Ascites) [29, 30, 33, 34]
 Yarqan (Jaundice) [20][29][30][33][34]
 Kirme Shikam (Helminths) [30][34]
 Wajaul Mafasil (Arthralgia) [20][30][34]
 Laqwa (Facial Palsy), Sara (Epilepsy), Sakta (Apoplexy) and Bawaseer (Piles) [41]
 Ehtabase Haiz (Amenorrhoea) [30][32][34]
 Zeequn Nafas (Asthma) [20][30][32][34]
 Suda Balghami (Phlegmatic Headache) [19]
 Zukam (Rhinites) [40]
 Balghami Amraz (Phlegmitic disease) [34]
 Suale Balghami (Phlegmatic cough) [29][31][33]
 Darde Sadar (Chest pain) [29][31][33]
 Intesabe Tanaffus (Dyspnoea) [29][33][39]

Kharji Istemal (External uses):**Tela:**

Bars (Vitiligo) [19][20][30][33][34][38]
 Bahaq (Pityriasis) [20][30][34][38][39]
 Qooba (Ring worm infection) [20][30][34]
 Muhasa (Warts) [30][32][34][39][40]
 Suda Barid (Headache phlegmatic) [32][40]
 Khelan (Mole) [29][32][37][38][39]
 Mankoos (Lentigo) [29] **Zemad:**
 Mukhrije Deedan [19][29]. Qatile Deesan [32] (Apply on umbilicus).
 Bars, Suda, Kharish (Itching), Wajaul Mafasil [33], Warm (Inflammation) [29][32][33][39].

Nushooq (Inhalation):

Shaqqeeqa (Migrain) [30][34]
 Nazla, Zukam [19][29][32][34][37]
 Suda Muzmin (Chronic Headache) [30][34][39]
Qutoor: Yarqan (powder with woman milk) [19][29][34] Zukam [19][32]
Bakhoor: Zukam [30][34]
Gharghara: Darde Daant (Odontalgia) [19][33][32][39][40]
Zaroor: Bawaseer [19][29]

Mizaj (Temperament):

Har Yabis (Hot and Dry) 3⁰ [19][64][33][39][41][42], Har Yabis (Hot and Dry) 2⁰ [29][34][30][38]

Part used: Seed [21][22][23][26], Fruit [21][23]

Muzirat (Side effects):

Khunaq (Diphtheria) [29][32][33][34][41] Daurane (Vertigo) [33][29][34][30], Riya (Flatulence) [29]

Musleh (Corrective):

Kateera (Sterculia urenus) [29][30][33][34][41] Sirka (Vinegar) [29][33] Tabasheer (Bambusa arundinacea) [29].

Badal (Substitute):

Aneesoon (Pimpinella anisum) [29][30][33][34] Shibat (Anethum sowa) [29][33] Tukhme Reshad (Lipidium Sativus) [29].

Doses:

1-3 Gram [17]
 3-7 Gram [21]
 1-2 Masha [30][34][38]
 1-2 Gram [20]
 1-3 Masha [34]
 0.6-1.2 Gram [43]

Ethno Botanical actions:

It decreased serum Cholesterol, serum LDL, serum Triglyceride and increase serum HDL[44]

Aromatic [17][18][56]	Stimulant [56][25][43][45]
Carminative [25][27][43][44][45]	Diuretic [17][18][25][26][45]
Emmanogogue [18][22][23][28]	Galactogogue [17][27][33][36][45]
Diaphoratic [17][18][23][43]	Antibillious [18][23][56][27]
Anodyne [56][28]	Antibacterial [56][28][43][45]
Anti-inflammatory [56][28]	Appetizing [56][28]
Digestive [27][26][28][43]	Anthelmintic [56][27][36]
Febrifogue [56][28]	Sudorific [28]
Expectorant [56][28]	Stomachic [18][26][27][43]
Detergent [31]	Suppurative [31]
Uterine contraction [18][23][25][26][36]	Aphrodisiac [26]

Abortifacient, Amebicide, Analgesic, Anesthetic, Anti-amphetamine, Antiseptic, Bronchodilator, Cardio-depressant, Depressant, Antidote, Antihistaminic, Antioxidant, Antispasmodic, Antiviral, Contraceptive, Cyclooxygenase inhibitor, Fungicide, Hepatoprotective, Hypotensive, Hypoureemic, Immunostimulant, Insecticide, Laxative, 5-Lipoxygenase, Phagocytotic, Vermifuge and Uterocontractant [43].

Therapeutic Uses:

Puerperal fever [18][25][26]	Eruption of skin [18][22][23][56]
Scorpion sting [18][22][43][45]	Amenorrhoea [17][18][23][28]
Dysmenorrhoea [17][18][23][27]	Haemorrhoids [56][28][43]
Jaundice [56][28][43]	Inflammation [56][28][43]
Fever [18][56][27][28][43]	Anorexia [56][28][43]
Dyspepsia [17][28][43]	Flatulence [26][28][43]
Diarrhoea [56][28][43]	Dysentery [56][28][43]
Cough [28][43][45][56]	Stranguary [56][28]
Indigestion [56][37][28]	Loss of appetite [56][27][28]
Dropsy [17][18][56]	Abortion (excess amount) [18][27][36]
Bronchial asthma [45][46]	

Worm infestation [18], Paralysis [56], Abdominal lump, Rheumatism [26], Diabetes, Hypertension [46],.

Chemical constituents:Organic:

Essential oil [20][22][28] Fixed oil [17][18][36], Saponin [17][20][36], Tannin [20][21], Alkaloids [17][21], toxic glucosides [18][21][22][28], Melanthin (bitter substance) [18][22][28][36], Albumin, Sugar, Mucilage, Organic acid, Metarbin, arabic acid [36], Volatile oil [18], Resin [20], Steroid [21].

Inorganic:

Aluminium and magnesium [21], Copper, Zinc, Phosphorous [35], Iron, Calcium [17][21].

Phytochemical:

Nigellidine, Nigellicine and Nigellimine. Thymole, Dithymoquinone and Momoterpenes [17]. Linoleic acid, Palmitic acid, Stearic acid and Oleic acid [17][25][35], Lenolenic acid, Myristic acid [25][35], Palmitoleic acid and Arachidonic acid [35]. Arginin, Methionine, Nigellone, 4-terpineol, Carvone, Thymoquinone [44]. Thiamin, Riboflavin, Pyridoxin, Niacin and Folacin [35].

Scientific Report:

1. *Nigella sativa* produces antiatherogenic effect by decreasing low density lipoprotein cholesterol level; it also increases high density lipoprotein level [47].
2. 180mg of *Nigella sativa* seed, powder along with statin (10-20mg), controlled with statin (10-20mg). Combination with *Nigella sativa* shows significant ($P<0.05$) decrease in cholesterol, LDL, VLDL and triglycerides, and significant increase of HDL. So it decreased coronary artery disease risks [48].
3. *N. sativa* seeds in the diet have favorable effect on lipid profile by lowering the triglyceride, total cholesterol, LDL and increasing the HDL cholesterol in albino rats[49].
4. Present study clearly shows that *N. sativa* seed possess significant anti-metabolic syndrome, it has slightly anorexic effect which exerted beneficial action on serum lipids and weight gain [50].
5. *N. sativa* oil has significant effect on diabetic and dyslipidemic patients, and found to be effective as add on therapy in patients of insulin resistance syndrome [51].
6. *N. sativa* has effect on dyslipidemia, and hyperglycemia so it has protective activity on cardiovascular system[52] [53]
7. *N. sativa* seed extract could be a supplement, as an antioxidant therapy and may be beneficial for correcting hyperglycemia and preventing diabetic complications due to lipid peroxidation and free radical oxidants [53] [54]
8. *N. sativa* and Thymoquinone produce significant hypoglycemic in albino rats[55].
9. Antibacterial activity: Thymohydroquinone obtained from volatile oil of *Nigella sativa* showed, Antimicrobial effect against Gram positive microorganism. Essential oil showed Antibacterial activity against *Bacillus pumilus*, *staphylococcus lutea* and *vibrio cholera*. Antifungal activity against *Aspergillus* species and *Curvularia lunata* [56].
10. Thymoquinone and Thymohydroquinone have inhibitory and lethal effects against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and when combined with antibiotics they may exert synergistic activity [52][53][57].
11. Long term use of *Nigella sativa* increase effect on fertility and reproductive system in adult male rat [58].
12. *N. sativa* is an effective in opioid dependence; it treated the opioid withdrawal syndrome [59].
13. *N. sativa* L. seed extract modulates the neurotransmitter [60].
14. Extracts of *N. sativa* seeds have protective effects against ischemia in rat[61]
15. *Nigella Sativa* seeds supplementation with the high fructose diet in rats decreased visceral adiposity, insulin resistance, hyperlipidemia hypoadiponectinemia[62]
16. Antioxidant, Hepatoprotective, Anti ulcer activity in GIT, Anti inflammatory action of *Nigella sativa*[52][53].
17. *Nigella sativa* oil is effective in lower respiratory tract illness, due to its possible relaxant effect[63][64][65][66]

DISCUSSION

Though *Kalawnji* has been in practice since centuries to treat various types of metabolic disorders in Unani medicine, this review paper is a concerted attempt to bring it to medical domain for the larger benefit.

In the study of AburRasheed[67], *Kalawnji* has effect on almost all parameters but statistically significant result was only on total cholesterol and HDL cholesterol. While in other studies, extract of *Nigella sativa* has effect on lipid profile, it decreases intracellular cholesterol due to an upregulation of LDL receptors, mentioned by Inayatullah Bhatti *et al* (2009) [47]. Supplementation of *Nigella sativa* seed has favourable effect on lipid profile this may be due to possible choleric activity. The choleric function of *N. sativa* is either by reducing the synthesis of cholesterol through hepatocytes or by decreasing or its fractional reabsorption through small intestine Mohammad Anwar Buriro, Mohammad Tayyab (2007) [49]. *N. sativa* is effective in lowering the cholesterol level and improving the lipid profile, possible mechanism may be either inhibit cholesterol synthesis or stimulates bile acid excretion. It is known that both effects would leads to a decrease in serum cholesterol. Another mechanism that was proposed that *N. sativa* increases the production of LDL receptors (Ahmad Najami 2008) [51]. Another study is suggested that *N. sativa* has slight anorexic effect causes hypolipidemic effect by Ashish S Fhadekar (2007)[32].

The normal ratio of cholesterol and HDL is ≥ 4.5 , recommended by Harrison's Internal medicine [33].

CONCLUSION

Kalawnji plays important role in the management of PCOS, provided that the drug should be used judiciously with all the facts taken into consideration. Besides the fundamental importance of this pharmacotherapeutic methodology there is a problem of lack of uniform standardisation. It therefore apparently seems essential to standardize it and to develop certain scientific parameters for evaluation of the efficacy of this drug as it is cost effective, user friendly devoid of adverse effects. Hence scientific studies are being under taken to validate this age old drug in different Unani research institutions of India so that the benefits may be reaped by large section of society. This therapy must also be evaluated for prophylactic use so that some of the impending attacks / bouts of disease can be averted.

List of abbreviations:

PCOS	Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome	et al	Et alii or et alia (and others)	<i>N. sativa</i>	<i>Nigella sativa</i>	p	P value
HDL	High density lipoprotein	<	Lesser than,				
LDL	Low density lipoprotein	>	Greater than				
VLDL	Very low density lipoprotein	≤	Lesser or equal to				
GIT	Gastrointestinal tract	≥	Greater or equal to				

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The Authors duly acknowledge the coordination and cooperation extended by Assistant Director Incharge and the library staff of Central library, Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine, Srinagar, in collecting the literature pertaining to the manuscript, authors whose references quoted and the journal reviewers for pointing out certain discrepancies. There is no any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Nicholas A.boom, et al. Davidson's principles and practice of Medicine, 21st edn, Churchill Livingstone Elsevier. 2010. p. 760.
2. Dewhurst's. Textbook of Obstetrics and Gynecology, 7th edn, edited by D.Keith Edmonds, printers publishers.2007. p.381.
3. D.C. Dutta .Text book of gynecology 6th edn, New Delhi: New Central book agency (P) LTD. 2013.P.440.
4. Dale R. Dunnihoo, Fundamentals of Gynecology & obstetrics. Printer R.R.Donnelley and sons.p. 210.
5. Razi ABZ. *Al Hawi - fil - tib* .Vol.9. New Delhi: CCRUM .2001. pp.153,163,168
6. K D Tripathi, essentials of medical pharmacology, 6th edn. New Delhi. Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers (p) LTD.2010. 269,304.
7. Sharma & Sharma's, Principles of pharmacology, 3rd edn. New Dehli. Paras Medical Publisher, pp.593, 646.
8. Harrison's.Principles of internal medicine .18th edn. Mc Graw Hill.2008. vol. I .p.387
9. Qumri AMH. .*Ghina Muna*. Ist edn .New Dehli .CCRUM.2008.p.410.
10. Khan.M.A.*Akseer-e-Azam*:urdu translation by Hakim Kabir u din.Idara Kitabu Shifa. New Delhi.2011.p.797.
11. Hakim kabir u din, *Makhzanul Mufaridat*. Lahore .Sidiqui Publisher house pp.460, 461.
12. Ghani H.M.N. *Khazanul-ul-Advia*. New Delhi .Idrar Kitabul shifa. Vol.Ist – fourth.p.1061
13. Ibn Baitar, *Al Jamiul Mufaridat Advia wa Agzia* .New Dehli. CCRUM .vol.3. p.272.
14. Dr. M.I.H. Farooqi. Tib E Nabwi aur Nabatat Ihadees. Ist edn. Lukhnow. Sidra publisher. 2010. P.59.
15. Dr. Khalid Gajnavi, Tibb-e-Nabvi aur Jadeed Science, ist edn. Matiya Mahal Dehlii-6.Adbi Duniya publication 1990.p.235.
16. Ali Bin Ahmad Bin Ali Bin Hubul Bagdadi, *Al mukhtarat fil tib*.urdu translation. New Delhi.CCRUM.vol.2.p.268.
17. Williamson E. M. Major Herbs of Ayurveda. London: Churchill Livingstone; 2002: 196-98.
18. Nandkarni KM. Indian Materia Medica Vol. 1. Mumbai: Papular Parkashan Private Limited; 1982: 854-57.
19. Ibn Qeem Shamsuddin. Tib Nabvi. Mumbai: Al Darul Salfia; 2008: 553-56.
20. Anonymous. The Unani Pharmacopia of India. Vol. 1(1). New Delhi: AYUSH; 2007: 42-43.
21. Anonymous. Standardization of Single Drug of Unani medicine. Part 2. New Delhi: CCRUM; 1992: 196-200.
22. Anonymous. Medicinal plants in Folklores of Southern India. 1st ed. New Delhi: CCRUM; 2001: 117.
23. Anonymous. Medicinal Plants of India. Vol. 2. New delhi: ICMR; 1987: 337-40.
24. Parjapati Narayan Das, Kumar U. Agros's Dictionary of Medicinal Plants. Jodhpur: Agrobios; 2005: 226.
25. Khare C.P. Indian Medicinal Plants. New Delhi: Springer Science; 2007: 439.
26. Chatterjee Asima, Pakrashi S. C. The Treatise on Indian Medicinal Olants. Vol. 1. New Delhi: CSIR; 2005:140-41.
27. Nandkarni K. M. Indian Plants and Drugs. New Delhi: Srishti Book Distributers; 2005: 259-60.
28. Pullaiah T. Encyclopaedia of World Medicinal Plants. Vol. 3. New Delhi: Regency Publication; 2006:1409.
29. Ghani Najmul. Khazainul Advia. New Delhi: Idara Kitabul Shifa; YNM: 1061-62.
30. Ghulam Nabi Munshi. Makhzanul Mufradat wa Murakkabat. New Delhi: CCRUM; 2007: 100.
31. Ibn Baitar Ziauddin A. Aljamiul Mufradat Al Advia Wal Aghzia (Urdu). Vol.3. New Delhi: CCRUM; YNM: 156-58.
32. Abdul Hakeem. Bustanul Mufradat. New Delhi: Idara Kitabul Shifa; 2002: 450-51
33. Kabeeruddin. Makhzanul Mufradat (Khawasul Advia). New Delhi: Ejaz Publishing House; YNM: 460-61.
34. Jacqueline L. Longe. The Gale Encyclopedia of Alternative Medicine. Vol. 1. USA: Thomson Gale; 2005:244-47.
35. Dymock William. Pharmacographia Indica. Vol. 1. New Delhi: Srishti Book Distributers; 2005:28-29.
36. Ibn Rushd. Kitabul Kulliyat (Urdu). New Delhi: CCRUM; 1987: 294.
37. Kabeeruddin. Ilmul Advia Nafeesi. New Delhi: Ejaz Publishing House; 2007: 189-90.
38. Ibn Sina. Alqanoon (Urdu translation by Ghulam Hasnain Kantoori) Vol. 2. New Delhi: Idara Kitabul Shifa; YNM: 454.
39. Ibine Hubl Muhazzabuddin. Al mukhtarat Fil Tib. New delhi: CCRUM; 2005. 2:268.
40. Abdul Haleem. Mufradate Azeezi. New Delhi: CCRUM; 2009. 17.
41. Ibn Sina. Alqanoon Fil Tib (Arabic) Vol. 2. New Delhi: Jamia Hamdard; 1408 H: 252-53.
42. Duke James A. Hand Book of Medicinal Herbs. USA: CRC Press LLC: 2002: 88-89.
43. Duke, James A. CRC Hand Book of Medicinal Spices. USA: CRC Press LLC: 2003: PNM.
44. Anonymous. The useful Plants of India. New Delhi: CSIR; 2006: 399.
45. Mukharjee P., Houghton P. J. Evaluation of Herbal Medicinal Products. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2009: 209.
46. Ahmad Iqbal, Aqil Farrukh, Owais Mohammad. Modern Phyto Medicine. Weinheim: Wiley- VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA. 2006: 130.
47. Bhatti Inayatullah, Rahman F, Khan M Aslam, Khan Marwat S. *Effect of prophetic medicine Kalawnji (Nigella sativa) on lipid profile of human being: an in vivo approach*. World applied science journal. 2009; 6 (8):1053-1057.
48. Tasawar Zahida, Siraj Zeshan, Ahmad Nisar, Lashari MH. *The effect of Nigella sativa on lipid profile in patients with stable coronary artery disease in Multan, Pakistan*. Pakistan journal of nutrition. 2011; 10 (2): 162-167.
49. Buriro Mohammad Anwar, Tayyab M. *Effect of Nigella sativa on lipid profile in albino rats*. Gomal journal of medical sciences. 2007 (Jan- June); Vol.5, No.1: 28-31.

50. Parhizkar Saadat, Latiff Latiffa A, Rahman Sabria A and Dollah Mohammad A. *Preventive effect of Nigella sativa on metabolic syndrome in menopause induced rats*. Journal of medicinal plant research. 2011; Vol 5(8): 1478-1484.
51. Najmi Ahmad, Naseeruddin M, Khan Rahat A, Haque Shahzad F. *Effect of Nigella sativa oil on various clinical and biochemical parameters of insulin resistance syndrome*. International journal of diabetes in developing countries. 2008; Vol 28 (1): 11-14.
52. Paarakh Padma M. *Nigella sativa- A comprehensive review*. Indian journal of natural products and resources. 2010; Vol 1(4):409-4029
53. Gilani A Hasan, Jabeen Qaisar, Khan M Asadullah. *A review of medicinal uses and pharmacological activities of Nigella sativa*. Pakistan journal of biological sciences. 2004; 7(4): 441-445
54. Kaleem M, Kirmani D, Asif M, Bano Bilqees and Ahmad Q. *Biochemical effect of Nigella sativa seeds in Diabetic rats*. Indian journal of experimental biology. 2006; Vol 6: 745-748
55. Hawsawi Zubaida A, Ali Basli A, Bamosa Abdulla O. *Effect of Nigella sativa (Black seed) and thymoquinone on blood glucose in albino rats*. Annals of Saudi medicine. 2001; Vol. 21, No. 3-4: 242-
56. Ray AB, Sharma BK, Singh UP. *Medicinal Properties of Plants*. Lucknow: Inter National Book Distributing Co.; 2004. 389-90.
57. Halawani Eman. *Antibacterial activity of thymoquinone and thymohydroquinone Nigella sativa and their interaction with some antibiotics*. Advance in biological research. 2009; 3(5-6): 148-153.
58. Muhammad Mukhallad A, Mohammad MMJ, Dradka Hatham. *Effect of black seed on spermatogenesis and fertility of male albino rats*. Research journal of medicine and medical sciences. 2009; 4 (2):386-390
59. Sangi Sibghatullah. Ahmad Shahida P. Channa M aslam, Ashfaq M, Mastori S. Murad. *A new and novel treatment of opioid dependence*. J Ayub Med. Coll. Abbotabad (<http://www.ayubmed.edu.pk/JAMC/past/20-2/sangi.pdf>). 2008; 20(2).
60. El-Naggar Tarek, Palomino OlgaMar'ia, Arce Carmen, and Carretero Mar'ia Emilia. *Nigella sativa L. seed extract Modulates the neurotransmitter amino acids release in cultured neurons in vitro*. Journal of Biomedicine and Biotechnology. Article ID 398312. 2010: 8.
61. Hosseinzadeh Hossein, Jaafari Mahmoud Reza, Khoei Ali Reza and Massoud Rahmani. *Anti-ischemic Effect of Nigella sativa L. Seed in Male Rats*. Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. 2006; 1: 53-58
62. Bahgat Nehal M., Soliman Ghada Z. A. *Effect of Nigella Sativa Supplementation in Diet on Metabolic Syndrome in Aged Rats*. Journal of American Science. 2011; 7(7): 577-583.
63. Ahmad Jameel, Khan Rahat A, Malik M Ashraf. *A study of Nigella sativa oil in the management of wheeze associated lower respiratory tract illness in children*. African journal of pharmacy and pharmacology. 2010; Vol 4(7): 436-439.
64. Altaf Rabia, Asmawi Mohammad Zaini, Dewa Aidiahmad and Umar Muhammad Ihtisham. *Sources and possible mechanisms of action of important phytoconstituents with cardiovascular properties*. African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology. 2012; Vol. 6(9). 563-580.
65. Lango Dan L. et al. *Harrison's Principle of Internal Medicine 18th ed. Vol.2, USA: Mc Graw Hill Companies; 2012: 3146-3156.*
66. Ibne Sina. *Al Qanoon Fit Tib (Urdu translated by Kantoori GH). Vol 3. New Delhi: Idara Kitabushifa; 2007.p. 1120-21.*
67. Abdur Rasheed, *Therapeutic evaluation of Kalonji (Nigella sativa) in dyslipidemia [Dissertation], National Institute of Unani Medicine, RGUHS, Bangalore. 2012.*

54878478451180503

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

- Convenient online manuscript submission
- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- International recognition
- No space constraints or color figure charges
- Immediate publication on acceptance
- Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories
- Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

